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IMMIGRATION FROM RUSSIA TO THE UNITED STATES FOR THE LAST TWO YEARS

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Abstract

We interviewed immigrants who arrived in the US from Russia over the past 2 years. Of course, it is not the first attempt to evaluate immigration from Russia, but the results obtained are interesting because they may reflect the true reasons for the immigration of Russians.

Since the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, Russians have been immigrating to other countries - some because of disagreement with the war, and someone because of the risk of going to the front as part of the mobilization. Forbes, citing estimates from the Kremlin, reported that 700,000 people had left the country since the start of mobilization [1].

Keywords: immigration, Russian immigrants.

At least 300,000 Russian citizens last year made the long journey from Russia to the United States. Most of them sought political asylum in the US. In this article we will talk about the largest wave of immigration from Russia to the US in recent 2 years looks like.

The term refers to the relocation of a citizen from one country to another for economic, political, and other reasons [2].

For the first time, the outflow of the population occurred during the time of the Russian Empire. This became possible after allowing free travel abroad. Several waves of emigration were observed in the USSR and modern Russia [3].

Scientists compare the emigration wave of 2022 with white emigration during the October Revolution and the Civil War.

First-time immigrants from Russia arrived in the United States on both coasts beginning in the late 1800s. Nearly 3 million Russians arrived during the first wave of open immigration that began in the late 19th century and continued into the early 20th century. However, only about 20,000 people made it to America in the period after the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917 until World War II [4].

Nowadays, it becomes more and more difficult for Russian citizens to get to the United States. More recently, American consulates in Russia have completely stopped issuing visas to Russians. In pursuit of a dream, many are left with only one illegal option - to try to cross the US-Mexico border. However, to do this is not only difficult but also extremely dangerous.

USAFACT website gives government data that "In fiscal year 2021, there were 1,659,206 border encounters on the Southwest border of the US" [5].

The Kremlin-led war in Ukraine is forcing Russians to make a choice. And there are more and more people who are ready to take risks at the border, even with children. 20 Republican senators, concerned about the rise in the number of Russians illegally entering the US, call it a threat to national security. However, other politicians are calling on President Biden to speed up the brain drain from Russia and accept all those whom the Russian authorities brand as traitors to the motherland and national traitors. At least 700,000 people had left the country, according to OK Russians, a non-profit organization that helps Russians who disagree with the Kremlin's policy on the war in Ukraine [6].

In total, according to the UN, more than 10 million immigrants from Russia live abroad. This is the third largest figure after India and Mexico [7].

An accurate numerical estimate of emigration from Russia was not the aim of this research. The above data seem to us important in illustrating the magnitude of the phenomenon. Next, we will focus on the people who left: who are they, why did they leave, and what is it like for them in a new place as the US.

Methodology

We interviewed 450 people who left Russia from 2021 to 2023 and now live in the US. The link to the survey was distributed through Russian-speaking "emigrant" groups on social networks.

The coverage of the research (450 people aged 14 to 70 from 12 states in the US) suggests that the data obtained describe the phenomenon at least in the first approximation.

The reasons for moving:	%
Safety	95
Political situation	83
War in Ukraine	70
Caring for the future of children	73
Mobilization	65
New life experience	63
The level of tolerance in society	57
Wanted to live in this country	42
The quality of education	36
Infrastructure (roads, transport...)	26
Business conditions	16
Quality of cultural life	12
Family circumstances (marriage, relatives...)	7
Religious views	3

According to these data we can see that for new emigrants from Russia, their safety, stability and concern for the future of children are important - the main driving motives for people from these segments. For most respondents, Safe Environment is their choice. They are uncomfortable at home. There is a lot of politics in the motives of this part of the audience: they are not satisfied with the current regime, lack of freedoms,

Age of emigrants

Most (55%) of our respondents are between 25 and 45 years old. Only 15% are now more than 40 years old. The vast majority (85%) is in an official or civil marriage. Half have minor children. 92% of those who left have a higher education, and 17% have an academic degree. A third are self-employed (freelancers, entrepreneurs, company owners), and half are specialists.

At the time of the move, they were between 20 and 40 years old, and only a quarter had children.

The full ranking of the reasons for moving to the US looks like this.

Which of the following influenced your decision to move to US? (Multiple options could be selected)

corruption. This causes them fear, a sense of danger, hopelessness and hopelessness. Many have children, and concern for their future is an important reason for emigrating.

Respondents expressed their opinion about emigration and the following answers were the most frequent.

Respondents' answers	%
"I'm scared and feel bad in Russia due to War and mobilization. And I wanted my kids to grow up in a more open and free environment."	73
"Lack of political freedoms, lack of rights. The corruption of the police and the courts, the understanding that if something happens, no one will protect me."	68
"The political situation, the irrevocability of the political power, the feeling of insecurity. Having children gave me more determination to leave Homeland"	53
"We see no future in Russia either for ourselves or for our child."	49

The US as a new country is very good

The overwhelming majority (89%) of emigrants like to live in the United States. They rate their place of residence highly on such characteristics as safety, ecology, the level of tolerance in society and the stability of the situation in the country. This coincides with the reasons for the move - people got what they wanted.

I feel comfortable living and working in the US

Do you agree with the following statements? Shown % "rather" + "completely"	%
I do not plan to move from this country yet	86
I strive to learn the language of this country at a good level	83
I am comfortable with local codes of conduct and customs	76
I strive to integrate in this country	73
I will never become completely own in US	26
I feel like a stranger in this country	23

Most of the respondents (86%) are not yet planning a new move and strive to learn the English language at a good level (83%). Without a good knowledge of the language, life is uncomfortable almost everywhere. A 26% of respondents do not believe that this is possible in principle. And 23% of respondents complain and feel like strangers.

Russia is going the wrong way

Almost all those who left continue to follow the events in their homeland and, apparently, worry. Most of emigrants manage to make a living in a new place, rented houses and found a job. Only 8% depend on sources of income in Russia.

Almost all of the respondents believe that Russia is developing in the wrong direction. The news from Russia is negative and highly politicized.

Only 12% plan to return to their homeland, 20% do not deny such an opportunity for themselves, 68% will not return, most likely never.

This study is a meaningful reflection on the current migration waves in Russia, which are unknown to us. In this sense, the relevance of this survey lies in the fact that now there is no accurate information about those who have left, it is scattered. There is no complete picture, so we will continue our research and collect meaningful and up-to-date information about ongoing migration flows.

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